

Speculation on Quantum Bound Spatial Density, Dynamic Probability and Momentum

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A classical bound state may be described by kinetic energy at each x point (within dx). In quantum mechanics, this may only be done for average kinetic energy because a given p is automatically associated with an $\exp(ipx)$ which yields a wavelength \hbar/p and is linked with inherent conservation of momentum. In other words, conservation of momentum is key and a given p is linked with a resolution of \hbar/p . First, one may note that $\exp(ipx)$ really means $\exp(ip \int dx)$ for p constant because this probability cannot be origin specific. Secondly, it is a directional probability (p has a direction) with the probabilistic value seeming to be Δx because p is constant. This is unusual because $x=vt$ with $v=\text{constant}$ for velocity suggesting smooth x space. This is fact the case, but due to the dynamic probability $\exp(ipx)$ representing inherent conservation of momentum and a ruler gradation (the two are linked), one maps the gradations to a revolution of a circle such that $\exp(i d \theta)$ is the same for all $d \theta$, but there is an inherent gradation length of \hbar/p . In other words, different p represent different scaling of space.

For a single p , $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamical probability which represents more information than the uniform x probability existing in the \hbar/p length. To find how $\exp(ip \Delta x)$ is associated with spatial probability, one may consider Δx and then $-\Delta x$, or $\exp(ip \Delta x) \exp(ip (-\Delta x))$. This brings one back to $\Delta x=0$ and is linked with uniform probability in x space.

One may note that the dynamical probability $\exp(ip \Delta x)$ is not linked with motion in time, i.e. $x(t)$. If one has a quantum bound state, then there exists a potential in space $V(x)$ which renders impulse hits and creates various $\exp(ipx)$ s. In other words, momentum changes. If one were to create a mathematical average, $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, then these different probabilities exist at different times, but one is adding them with time removed. More interestingly, given $\exp(ip \Delta x)$, if one wishes to revert back to $\Delta x = 0$, then the momentum may have changed and one must consider all $\exp(ip \Delta x) \exp(ip_j (-\Delta x))$. Thus, even though both of these depend on uniformity of space, they are linked with different gradations, i.e. different scaling in space, and this product does not bring one back to $\Delta x = 0$. For a bound state there are momentum related probability terms $\exp(i(p_1 - p_2)x)$, which affect the spatial density. These integrate out (integral over dx), but do contribute to spatial density which is an average (throwing out time). In other words, the different length scales of $\exp(ipx)$ together with the desire to consider Δx and $-\Delta x$ lead to a $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$, in quantum mechanics, which gives spatial structure, but as noted this is ultimately linked to the form $\exp(ipx)$ and the fact that momentum is changed (not constant). Interesting, each x point maps to the same Eaverage, it is $P(x)$ which differs.

Classical Mechanics Versus Quantum Mechanics

Classical mechanics describes impulse hits and changes in momentum, but these occur at each dx . In other words, within a dx one has constant $v(x)$ to first order. Quantum mechanics on the other hand associates a dynamical probability $\exp(ip \Delta x)$ with a constant p . In other words, there is an inherent x resolution length \hbar/p and so the particle cannot be considered within dx , if $dx < \hbar/p$. Nevertheless, p still acts like an impulse and changes in p exist.

Thus, we note that the concept of p holds in quantum mechanics, but is automatically associated with $\exp(ipx)$ which is needed to inherently include conservation of momentum and create a ruler gradation for p . $\exp(ipx)$ is a dynamical probability which is associated with motion in one direction. It is, however, built on the assumption of uniform spatial probability within gradations. The stochastic variable is Δx for constant p , i.e. one really has $\exp(ip \Delta x)$ because the result cannot be origin dependent. $\exp(ipx)$ describes motion in a circle with each $d\theta$ yielding the same $\exp(i d\theta)$. Nevertheless, p represents a scaling in space, so even though one has uniform x probability within gradations, one cannot ignore the gradations and think that space is the same if one compares $\exp(ip_1x)$ and $\exp(ip_2x)$.

If, however, one considers $\exp(ip \Delta x)$ by itself, then there is only one scale in space, \hbar/p , and one may see the uniformity of space by considering:

$$\exp(ip \Delta x) \exp(ip (-\Delta x)) = 1 \quad ((1))$$

Thus, $\Delta x - \Delta x$ returns one to $\Delta x=0$, and the probability applies to $\Delta x=0$. Things, however, become very different in a quantum bound problem.

Quantum Bound Problem

The quantum bound problem must describe impulse hits on various $\exp(ipx)$ s. Only on average can one have:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

As a result, if one wishes to pull time completely out of the picture, one has a set of $\exp(ipx)$ s each of which exist at different times: $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

A key issue seems to be that if one wishes to use $\Delta x - \Delta x$, then one must allow for:

$$\exp(ip \Delta x) \exp(ip_2 (-\Delta x)) \quad ((3))$$

Because momentum is changing and one does not necessarily have the same scaling for Δx and $-\Delta x$. As a result of this change in scaling (\hbar/p) for p and p_2 , Δx and $-\Delta x$ does not return one to $\Delta x=0$. One still has a probability phase, $\exp(i(p-p_2) \Delta x)$. This integrates out, but is present in the spatial density which was supposed to remove the gradation

effects. The change of momentum shows that there is product mixing of these different gradations or scaling in space and so the momentum as a dynamical probability view yields the spatial density:

$$W^*(x)W(x) = \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \left\{ \sum_{k} a(k) \exp(ikx) \right\} \quad ((4))$$

This is thus a spatial density based on a momentum impulse hit picture with different scalings of space linked to different momenta changing the picture of x space being uniform and creating crests and troughs. At the level of single $\exp(ipx)$ one has uniform space within gradations, but the mixing of scaled space destroys this view and this mixing occurs because of changes in momentum.

As a result, we try to consider the reason behind the crests-troughs of the $W^*(x)W(x)$ prescription.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that the quantum free particle dynamical probability, $\exp(ip \Delta x)$, with Δx being the stochastic quantity, exists in the first place to describe impulse hits in a probabilistic way which include inherent conservation of momentum (i.e. ruler gradations \hbar/p) or certain scaling of space. $\exp(ipx)$ represents a circle with each $d\theta$ yielding the same dynamical probability within a circle revolution. Different p values, however, lead to different scaling of space. For a single $\exp(ip \Delta x)$, considering Δx and $-\Delta x$ leads to $\exp(ip \Delta x) * \exp(ip (-\Delta x))$ which describes $\Delta x = 0$. Thus, one sees that there is uniform probability in space.

In a bound problem, $V(x)$ creates various momentum changes and if one ignores time, then one has a set of probabilities $\exp(ip x)$ for different p values. Each of these represents uniform x probability within its own \hbar/p gradations, but there are different scalings of space which become an important consideration. One may no longer consider $\exp(ip \Delta x) \exp(ip (-\Delta x))$ because p may have changed due to a collision with $V(x)$. One must consider $\exp(ip \Delta x) \exp(ip' (-\Delta x))$ and so $\Delta x - \Delta x$ with the different p 's does not yield $\Delta x = 0$. One obtains a phase and so there is no longer spatial uniformity even if one tries to remove the gradations. This, however, is due to the momentum picture $\exp(ipx)$ and the changing of momentum. Thus, $W^*(x)W(x)$ should be considered within this context. We thus try to account for the crests and troughs of W^*W in this manner.